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Research on the structure of corporate financial management objective system based on BRP method

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Abstract

Exploring the architecture of corporate financial management objectives of the BRP method is to help companies achieve revenue growth. In this paper, we analyze the motivation for implementing business process reengineering and constructing an intelligent financial management system based on the BRP method and intelligent technology. The DSBPR data analysis and processing model is constructed by using Bayesian ranking model combined with similarity in heterogeneous information networks in the intelligent financial management system. The intelligent financial management system constructed in this paper is analyzed in terms of the operating capacity and profitability of the enterprise. From the viewpoint of operating capability, the turnover rate of receivables, total assets, and current assets decreased by 87.17%, 91.85% and 49.68%, respectively in ten years, and the change rate of inventory turnover was 7.91%. In terms of profitability, there is a difference of 166.12% between the maximum and minimum values of return on net assets. This shows that the use of an intelligent financial management system can provide intuitive data analysis for enterprise development, which helps enterprises to target the coordinated development of enterprise strategies and thus promote the improvement of economic returns.

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1 Introduction

In the era of big data, the status of data assets in the process of enterprise development is becoming more and more important, and at the same time, the era of big data has also brought a huge impact on the traditional financial management of enterprises, and the innovation of practical enterprise financial management has been imminent [1-2]. Enterprise financial management has the characteristics of a large variety and quantity of data information, and the intelligent level of financial management can be comprehensively improved with the help of big data technology in enterprise financial management. Therefore, the intelligent construction of financial management is crucial in enterprise financial management under the current economic situation [3-5].

With the continuous development of global economic integration, the management and operation methods of enterprises directly determine the competitiveness of enterprises in the industry and the economic benefits obtained by them [6-7]. In the age of intelligence, the rapid spread and development of computer technology, Internet technology, and cloud computing have brought new challenges for enterprises to acquire resources and make full use of them [8-9]. Under such favorable development opportunities, the only way for enterprises to enhance the effectiveness of digital resource management and maintain the synchronous development with the business management level of enterprises is to ensure that they are at a normal level of development in the fierce competitive environment and to continuously promote the financial situation of enterprises to a better direction [10-11].

There are many factors affecting the innovation of enterprise financial management systems, and the literature [12] constructed the enterprise financial risk evaluation model through BP neural network can make an effective judgment on enterprise financial management and use it to improve the accuracy of prediction for enterprise financial risk. The literature [13] found that the ESG management of enterprises can have different degrees of influence on the financial management, marketing, and export performance diversification of enterprises and can also provide the corresponding theoretical basis to support the effective financial management of enterprises. The literature [14] shows that there is a non-linear relationship between financial performance and environmental performance in low-carbon and high-carbon-intensive firms, and firms can effectively regulate financial management through the interaction of financial performance and environmental performance.

In addition, the literature [15] argues that green innovation has a positive linear influence on corporate financial performance indicators and that companies can effectively improve resource utilization and corporate innovation image through green innovation, which in turn promotes the development of corporate products and thus improves corporate financial performance management. The literature [16] demonstrated the relationship between corporate financial management and corporate financial performance, operational efficiency, and financial decision management, and concluded that there is a significant positive influence between corporate decision-makers and corporate financial management, and that the role of clear decision-makers can effectively improve corporate competitiveness. The literature [17] shows that there is a positive and significant influence between corporate ESG management information disclosure and corporate management efficiency, and that companies can enhance their social responsibility choices through effective ESG activities, thus providing new paths for corporate sustainability.

In order to clarify the application of the BRP method in the structure of the enterprise financial management goal system, this paper firstly gives the application of business process reengineering in enterprise financial management and also the motivation for implementing business process reengineering. Then, based on the BRP method and intelligent technology, the intelligent financial

management system is constructed, and the similarity and Bayesian ranking models in the heterogeneous information network are used to process and analyze the financial data. Finally, Company S is used as an example to illustrate the effectiveness of the application of the intelligent financial management system on corporate earnings by analyzing the impact of the implementation of the intelligent financial management system on the operating capacity and profitability of Company S. From the analysis results; it shows that the intelligent financial management system based on BRP method and intelligent technology can effectively improve the economic profitability of the company.

2 Application of business process reengineering in enterprise financial management

The process is generally defined as a series of continuous activities designed to achieve a specific goal in a specific form. The traditional enterprise management process model is usually function-centered, which gradually highlights its backward and inefficient drawbacks under the current rapidly changing market economy, limiting the further development of the enterprise.

The purpose of business process reengineering is to improve the efficiency of enterprises, reduce operating costs, improve product quality, and maintain the dominant position of enterprises in the market competition. This chapter focuses on the impact of business process reengineering on the structure of enterprise financial management objective system, which provides theoretical support for the financial intelligence system built by integrating intelligent technology later.

2.1 Business Process Reengineering

Business process reengineering is the fundamental rethinking and radical redesign of an organization's business processes in order to achieve significant improvements in important indicators of performance such as cost, quality, service, and efficiency. It consists of four core issues, i.e., a rethinking of fundamental issues, radical redesign, significant progress, and important elemental processes.

2.1.1 Business process re-engineering changes

The core idea of business process reengineering is to re-engineer and redesign the existing business processes of an enterprise so that the key performance indicators of the enterprise can be significantly improved. The process reengineering approach involves the participation of employees in the reevaluation and redesign of existing processes, retaining and adding valuable processes, and discarding non-valuable ones. The target of the reengineering is the existing business processes with potential risks, and the purpose of the reengineering is to better serve customers and improve their satisfaction. The scope of change in business process reengineering is shown in Figure 1, which represents the process by which process reengineering can effectively reverse the transformation of a company [18].

Figure 1. Scope of BRP change

2.1.2 Ideas for Business Process Reengineering

The business process reengineering approach for corporate financial management objectives or the level of comprehensive corporate management consists of three main steps, namely, identifying the project, creating new business processes, and integrating the processes into the appropriate organization. The specific implementation steps and methods are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. BRP implementation process and method

BRP implementation process	Application method
Set up project team	-
Develop objectives	-
Business Process Analysis	ASME Process Analysis
Solution Proposal	Brainstorming
Solution feasibility assessment	Delphi Method
Construction of Information System	Smart Technology
Intelligent financial management system implementation	-

Through the identified business process reengineering project team, we analyze the problems of the existing enterprise financial management target system and then integrate intelligent technology to realize the construction of an intelligent financial system after a comprehensive evaluation, and then assist the implementation of an intelligent financial management system.

2.2 Motivation for implementing BPR

2.2.1 The effect of 3C environment on BRP

BRP implementation is to cope with 3C motives both customers, competition, and changing competitive environment. The motives of BRP implementation are divided into two kinds of external and internal factors, the external factors are mainly changing emerging markets, customer demand, and competition for IT capability, and the internal factors are mainly looking for survival opportunities, finding new economic growth point, and seeking competitiveness improvement. The internal factors exist mainly to cope with the changes of external factors. Figure 2 shows the relationship between internal and external factors and BRP.

Figure 2. The motivation relationship of BRP

2.2.2 Impact of Technology Adoption on BRP

The Technology Acceptance Model indicates that when an individual is stimulated externally, there is a certain perception of the individual’s usefulness and ease of use, and this perceived situation, in turn, has a certain influence on the individual’s behavior in using smart technology. The logical relationship between the TAM model’s external variables affecting people is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. TAM model

TAM describes how external variables affect the two main factors of ease of use perception and usefulness perception, thus changing human attitudes and intentions toward using technology, which also shows that BRP cannot be implemented without the support of intelligent information technology.

3 Enterprise financial management goal system - intelligent

Emerging technologies such as big data, cloud computing, and artificial intelligence are changing day by day, and their applications are gradually expanding, and they are constantly introduced into financial management, which has a profound impact on the change of financial system and drives more and more financial work from accounting-based to management-based. Based on the previous discussion of BRP theory, which also illustrates the role of intelligent information technology in promoting the construction of an intelligent system for enterprise financial management objectives, this chapter focuses on the effective establishment of an intelligent financial management system.

3.1 Framework construction of intelligent financial management system

3.1.1 Intelligent financial management system

An intelligent financial management system is a system that combines artificial intelligence and financial management together to be utilized, and this system can be said to be an extension of the development system of management accounting informatization. Management accounting is an important branch of current accounting development, and informatization is a technical means for the successful realization of management accounting concepts and methods. In order to standardize and guide enterprises to carry out management accounting informatization in an orderly, healthy, and efficient manner, the development system needs to be carefully conceived and laid out.

Intelligent financial management systems can interconnect business activities and financial activities of enterprises through business process reengineering as a whole and monitor each link in real-time. By displaying more intuitive data, it provides internal and external managers with an intelligent financial system for more rational and efficient decision-making.

3.1.2 Intelligent financial management system architecture

Intelligent financial management system architecture refers to the description of the logical relationship between the components of intelligent finance within the enterprise, and its basic framework is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Intelligent Financial Management System Architecture

Intelligent financial management system architecture mainly includes two core parts; one is the new generation of modern technology that provides support for intelligent finance, with big data, cloud computing, and other representative technologies injecting life into the realization of intelligent finance. The second is the functions that can be realized by intelligent finance, which can be realized from intelligent financial sharing, intelligent management accounting, intelligent big data management, etc.

3.1.3 Information processing of intelligent financial management system

Information processing in the intelligent financial management system mainly includes an intelligent financial sharing platform, intelligent management accounting platform, and intelligent big data management platform.

Intelligent financial sharing platform mainly solves the financial accounting work of enterprises, while paying more attention to the intelligent integration of business and finance.

Intelligent management accounting platform mainly solves the problems of internal production and operation and internal management of enterprises. The platform mainly uses data mining, data governance, and other technologies to intelligently manage accounting work, further guide the development of business work and reflect the high value-added work of enterprise finance.

The intelligent big data management platform mainly addresses issues such as data decision-making for enterprise-level management. Based on the intelligent financial sharing platform and intelligent management accounting platform, the platform mainly uses business intelligence, big data analysis, data governance, artificial intelligence, and other technologies to deal with various decision-making problems in enterprise production, operation, and management in real time, multi-dimensionally and visually, and provides more high value-added financial management activities such as production analysis, operation decision, management judgment, operation simulation and risk prediction for enterprises. Strong support.

3.2 Data Processing Techniques - Dual Similarity Bayesian Ranking Model

An intelligent financial management system needs to realize the interaction of enterprise financial information through efficient data processing technology and realize the effective classification of massive data by using the high similarity of data information. In turn, it provides technical support for the visualization of financial management data and also provides data support for the formulation of strategic decisions on the development of enterprise financial management through visualized reports. This section focuses on the technical theory related to the dual-similarity Bayesian ranking model.

3.2.1 Similarity in heterogeneous information networks

Heterogeneous information networks are a special class of information networks where the underlying data structure is a directed graph that includes multiple types of objects and multiple types of connections. In a heterogeneous information network, two different types of entities can be connected by different meta-paths, which shows a composite relationship between two different types of entities.

In this paper, we define $S_U^{(p)}$ denotes the matrix of similarity between manager and manager under a given meta-path $P_U^{(p)}$, $S_U^{(p)}(i, j)$ denotes the similarity between manager i and manager j before meta-path $P_U^{(p)}$. $S_I^{(q)}$ denotes the matrix of similarity between financial decision and financial decision under a given meta-path $P_I^{(q)}$, $S_I^{(q)}(i, j)$ denotes the similarity between financial decision i and financial decision j under a given meta-path $P_I^{(q)}$.

Since managerial and financial decisions have different similarities under different meta-paths, this paper regroups the weighted similarities by assigning weights to these paths. In this paper, we define S_U and S_I to represent the weighted similarity matrices of managerial and financial decisions on all meta-paths, respectively, and their specific computational expressions are:

$$S_U = \sum_{p=1}^{|P_U|} w_U^{(p)} S_U^{(p)} \quad (1)$$

$$S_I = \sum_{q=1}^{|P_I|} w_I^{(q)} S_I^{(q)} \quad (2)$$

Where $w_U^{(p)}$ denotes the weight of meta-path $P_U^{(p)}$ in all meta-paths P_U connecting managers and $w_I^{(q)}$ denotes the weight of meta-path $P_I^{(q)}$ in all meta-paths P_I connecting financial decisions.

3.2.2 Bayesian ranking model

The Bayesian ranking model is a pairwise ranking optimization scheme that employs a stochastic gradient descent method as an optimization model for the parameters [19]. Based on the assumptions of Bayesian theory, the objective of the Bayesian ranking model is to maximize the posterior probability, i.e:

$$p(\theta | >_u) \propto p(>_u | \theta) p(\theta) \quad (3)$$

Where θ denotes the parameter vector of an arbitrary model, such as a matrix decomposition model. The Bayesian ranking model has two underlying assumptions:

- 1) If the manager-finance decision pair (u, i) is observed, but the manager-finance decision pair (u, j) is not observed, then manager u prefers the financial decision i over financial decision j .
- 2) Each manager's decision-making behavior is independent of the other.

Based on these assumptions, the above likelihood function $p(>_u | \theta)$ can be redefined as:

$$\prod_{u \in U} p(>_u | \theta) = \prod_{(u, i, j) \in U \times I \times I} p(i >_u j | \theta)^{\delta((u, i) f (u, j))} \cdot (1 - p(i >_u j | \theta))^{[1 - \delta((u, i) f (u, j))]} \quad (4)$$

Where, $(u, i) f (u, j)$ indicates that manager u prefers financial decision i compared to financial decision j .

To accomplish the Bayesian model for the personalized sorting task, the Bayesian sorting model defines the individual probability that user u prefers item i over item j :

$$p(i >_u j | \theta) = \sigma(\hat{x}_{uij}) \quad (5)$$

Where σ is a logistic regression *sigmoid* function, when using matrix decomposition as a preference predictor, i.e., BPR-MF, when \hat{x}_{uij} can be defined as

$$\hat{x}_{uij} = \hat{x}_{ui} - \hat{x}_{uj} \quad (6)$$

In addition, the BPR model introduces a normal distribution conforming to a mean of zero and a variance of Σ_{θ} as the general prior probability density $p(\theta)$, so that the optimization equation can be derived as:

$$\sum_{(u,i,j) \in D_S} \ln \sigma(\hat{x}_{uij}) - \lambda_{\theta} \|\theta\|^2 \quad (7)$$

3.3 DSBPR algorithm design

This section focuses on the first algorithmic model proposed in Section 3.2, the personalized ranking model with dual similarity, which incorporates similarity information in a heterogeneous information network into a matrix decomposition algorithm based on the BPR model. Firstly, the definition of the standard rating predictor based on matrix decomposition is reviewed. Secondly, an improved model DSBPR incorporating similarity information in heterogeneous information networks is proposed, and finally, BPR is used as a parameter optimization model, and the learning algorithm for the parameters is given.

3.3.1 Preference predictor

The DSBPR preference predictor is based on the well-known scoring prediction model, the low-rank matrix decomposition, whose basic expression for predicting manager u 's preference for financial decision i is as follows:

$$r_{ui} = \alpha + \beta_u + \beta_i + p_u q_i^T \quad (8)$$

Where α represents the global rating bias, β_u, β_i represents the deviation terms of manager u and financial decision i , respectively, and p_u, q_i is an K -dimensional vector describing the implicit factors of manager u and financial decision i . The inner product of $p_u q_i^T$ expresses the relationship between manager u and the financial decision i , i.e., the extent to which the “potential preferences” of the manager are consistent with the “potential attributes” of the financial decision.

3.3.2 DSBPR model

Theoretically, the latent factor seems to reveal any relevant dimension. However, there are some “lone” financial decisions in the real scenario, and their associated history is too sparse, making it difficult to estimate their latent factors. Therefore, this paper needs to consider introducing more additional information into the scoring model to alleviate the above problem. Specifically, the similarity matrix between managers is added to the left side of inner product $p_u q_i^T$ and the similarity matrix between financial decisions is added to the right side of inner product $p_u q_i^T$, so that

$$R = \alpha + \beta^u + \beta^i + \frac{\mu \text{Sim}^u PQ^T}{\phi^u} + \frac{\gamma \text{Sim}^i PQ^T}{\phi^i} \quad (9)$$

Among them, R is a rating matrix of $m \times n$, α and β have the same meaning as equation (8) above, P and Q denote the hidden numerator matrices of $m \times k$ and $n \times k$, respectively, Sim^u is a user similarity matrix of $m \times m$, Sim^i is a similarity matrix of $n \times n$ goods, and here the text uses heterogeneous information networks to calculate the similarity matrix. In order to restrict the scoring matrix in a reasonable range of values, this paper introduces ϕ^u and ϕ^i as denominators in the fourth and fifth terms of the above equation (9), which ϕ^u and ϕ^i are both matrices of $m \times n$, and the specific definition form is:

$$\phi^u = \begin{pmatrix} \phi_{11}^u & L & \phi_{1n}^u \\ M & O & M \\ \phi_{m1}^u & L & \phi_{mn}^u \end{pmatrix} \quad (10)$$

$$\phi^i = \begin{pmatrix} \phi_{11}^i & L & \phi_{1n}^i \\ M & O & M \\ \phi_{m1}^i & L & \phi_{mn}^i \end{pmatrix} \quad (11)$$

Where each elementary term in the matrix is specifically defined in the form of:

$$\phi_{ij}^u = \sum_{l=1}^m \text{Sim}_{li}^u \quad (12)$$

$$\phi_{ij}^i = \sum_{l=1}^n \text{Sim}_{lj}^i \quad (13)$$

Since the inner product is calculated twice, the normalization parameter μ, γ is introduced and satisfies $\mu + \gamma = 1$.

3.3.3 DSBPR model learning

The learning of the DSBPR model is based on a Bayesian ranking model, and the widely used stochastic gradient descent algorithm is used for the optimization of the model in this paper, so the parameters of the model are updated as follows:

$$\theta \leftarrow \theta + \eta \left(\frac{e^{-\hat{x}_{uij}}}{1 + e^{-\hat{x}_{uij}}} \cdot \frac{\partial \hat{x}_{uij}}{\partial \theta} \right) + \lambda_{\theta} \theta \quad (14)$$

In each iteration, a sample is drawn uniformly from the data training set D_s consisting of (u, i, j) a triadic form, and the parameters are updated at the sampling points along the negative direction of the gradient of the loss function; figure 5 shows the basic flow of the DSBPR model. Specifically, and \hat{x}_{uij} the partial differentiation of each parameter is

$$\frac{\partial \hat{x}_{uij}}{\partial \theta} = \begin{cases} \frac{\mu Sim_u^u}{\phi_u^u} (Q_i - Q_j) + \gamma \left(\frac{Sim_i^i}{\phi_i^i} Q_i - \frac{Sim_j^j}{\phi_j^j} Q_j \right) & \text{if } \theta = P_u \\ \frac{\mu Sim_u^u}{\phi_u^u} P_u + \frac{\gamma Sim_i^i}{\phi_i^i} P_u & \text{if } \theta = Q_i \\ -\frac{\mu Sim_u^u}{\phi_u^u} P_u + \frac{\gamma Sim_j^j}{\phi_j^j} P_u & \text{if } \theta = Q_j \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

In addition, this paper uses three regular constraint terms, λ_p denotes the regular constraint term for managerial feature P , and two regular constraint terms are used for financial decisions, λ_{Q^+} for positive updates on financial decision feature Q_i , and λ_{Q^-} for negative updates on financial decision feature Q_j .

Figure 5. The basic process of DSBPR model

In summary, the DSBPR model is used for effective data analysis of managers and financial decisions in the intelligent financial management system to help enterprises build an intelligent financial

management system as a way to understand the business situation and better provide data analysis for enterprise development.

Through intelligent data processing technology, the business process reengineering method is used to adjust the organization form, financial process, and working method of the enterprise to further strengthen the construction of the enterprise's intelligent financial management system. In continuous exploration and practice, we constantly reconstruct and optimize business and financial processes to realize financial sharing services and provide suitable soil for the realization of enterprise intelligent financial management systems.

4 Intelligent financial management system operation financial capability evaluation analysis

In order to verify the effectiveness of the application of the intelligent financial management reminder constructed based on business process reengineering and intelligent data processing technology in this paper, the financial data of Company S for the decade 2011-2020 is selected as the research object in this paper for the case study. The financial capability of Company S after the operation of intelligent financial management system construction is evaluated and analyzed, and the impact of Company S on its corporate financial status through the implementation of intelligent financial management system construction is derived. The financial capability evaluation of the intelligent financial construction of Company S aims to control the construction and operation of intelligent financial management through various financial capability indicators and grasp the impact of the construction of an intelligent financial management system on the business situation of the enterprise. So that Company S can take timely measures to realize the improvement of financial capability and management so as to further enhance the competitiveness of the company.

4.1 Operating Capacity Analysis

An operating capacity analysis is to point out the direction for further improving the management level and enhancing the operating capacity of an enterprise. According to the actual situation of enterprises, indicators such as current asset turnover ratio, fixed asset turnover ratio, total asset turnover ratio, accounts receivable turnover ratio, and inventory turnover ratio can reveal the situation of capital turnover and resource allocation of enterprises, and promote enterprises to improve resource allocation. In order to examine the changes in the operating capacity of Company S, the data of accounts receivable turnover, inventory turnover, total asset turnover, and current asset turnover for each year are selected for comparative analysis in this section, and the results of the analysis are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Operating Capacity Analysis

The following conclusions can be drawn from the results of the analysis of Company S's operating capacity:

- 1) In terms of accounts receivable turnover rate, with the increase of years, the turnover rate of accounts receivable of Company S is decreasing year by year, from 34.15% in 2011 to 4.38% in 2020, which is a decrease of 87.17%, with more and more credit accounts, increasing the age of accounts, weakening the liquidity of assets, and increasing the risk of bad debts. This indicates that after the implementation of the intelligent financial management system construction, S Company's accounts receivable turnover problem has not improved and has not improved the enterprise's accounts receivable recovery ability.
- 2) In terms of inventory turnover rate, the inventory turnover rate of Company S has remained between 6.05% and 7.09% in ten years, with an overall change rate of 7.91% from 6.57% in 2011 to 7.09% in 2020, with less overall fluctuation, which indicates that Company S's product sales are normal. The inventory turnover ratio first shows a decreasing trend and then shows an increasing trend after the implementation of the intelligent financial management system, which indicates that the product sales are moving in a good direction.
- 3) In terms of total asset turnover ratio, S Company's total asset turnover ratio as a whole shows a downward trend from 2.59% in 2011 to 1.35% in 2020, a decrease of 91.85%, with lower investment efficiency of corporate assets and the need to improve sales capacity. The downward trend slowed down after the implementation of the intelligent financial system construction.
- 4) In terms of current asset turnover ratio, the current asset turnover ratio of Company S shows a decreasing trend in general, from 3.16% in 2011 to 1.59% in 2020, a decrease of 49.68%, and the changing trend is similar to the total asset turnover ratio. It indicates that the company's current assets are not utilized effectively, which wastes working capital and affects the profitability of the company.
- 5) Overall, the overall asset management level and operating capacity of Company S are poor, and it is necessary to consider more about the enterprise's own situation in the process of financial decision-making in the future and improve the asset management level as much as possible so as to improve the operating capacity of the enterprise.

4.2 Profitability Analysis

Profitability is an important indicator of business assessment; business operation is to obtain profit, and this indicator can analyze the ability of the enterprise profitability. It can reflect the enterprise's ability to obtain cash and cost reduction risk avoidance and other aspects of the ability to directly reflect the good or bad business results. In this section, four indicators reflecting profitability, ROE, NPC, NSM, and ROA, are selected for analysis, and the results are shown in Figure 7.

The following conclusions can be drawn from the results of the profitability analysis of Company S:

- 1) In terms of return on net assets, the return on net assets of Company S fluctuates widely over a ten-year period, with a difference of 166.12% between the highest and lowest return, which also indicates that the financial management process of enterprises is affected by the internal and external environment, and external policies may promote the increase in the scale of financing and thus the increase in the cost of financing. From the overall data, S enterprises are affected by both higher financing costs and intelligent financial management systems, resulting in higher fluctuation of short-term return on assets, but the overall trend indicates that S enterprises are still moving in a better direction.
- 2) In terms of cost margin, the overall fluctuation of S Company's cost margin is small, fluctuating between 0.83% and 3.27%, but with the implementation of the intelligent financial management system, the net cost profit of the enterprise shows an improving trend, so the implementation of the construction of S Company's intelligent financial management system has a positive impact on the net cost profit.
- 3) In terms of net sales margin and return on assets, the overall change of S Company is less volatile and similar compared to cost margin, which also indicates that the implementation of an intelligent financial management system can have a positive impact on the net sales margin and return on assets of the enterprise.

Figure 7. Analysis of profitability

In summary, Company S attaches great importance to corporate profitability in the process of financial management and shows an overall upward trend in corporate profitability after the implementation of the intelligent financial management system. At the same time, Company S also attaches importance to operating capability and has a good operating capacity.

In the operating capacity, the current asset turnover ratio has the highest weight, and the enterprise pays attention to the utilization rate of current assets, which is helpful for Company S to better capture the market. However, the analysis of financial data shows that the trend of current asset turnover of Company S is decreasing, and Company S should adjust its current asset management method.

In profitability, the return on net assets has the highest weight. By building up in the early stage, opening up the online and offline distribution network, and improving product quality and production speed, the company continues to drive the growth of its earnings in the market development opportunities, bringing long-lasting profits to the company.

5 Conclusion

In order to explore the architecture of enterprise financial management objectives based on the BRP method, this paper analyzes the application of business process reengineering in enterprise financial management. Based on the BRP method and intelligent technology, an enterprise intelligent financial management system is constructed, and the DSBPR model is used to realize the effective analysis of financial data. For the effectiveness of the application of an intelligent financial management system, the analysis of operating capacity and profitability was carried out with the example of Company S, and the following conclusions were drawn:

- 1) In terms of operating capacity, receivables turnover rate, total assets turnover rate and current assets turnover rate decreased by 87.17%, 91.85% and 49.68%, respectively in ten years, while inventory turnover rate fluctuated less with the change rate of 7.91%. This shows that the intelligent financial management system can effectively analyze the operating capacity of enterprises and also provide data support for enterprises to adjust their own financial management mode.
- 2) In terms of profitability, the return on net assets fluctuates the most, with a difference of 166.12% between the maximum and minimum return, while the cost margin, net sales margin, and return on assets fluctuate less. This indicates that the return on net assets will be directly affected by the internal and external factors of the enterprise, which also makes the enterprise take the initiative to strengthen the financial management construction in the process of competition, thus promoting the continuous increase of enterprise earnings.

In summary, S company, through the implementation of an intelligent financial management system that is conducive to the promotion of enterprise development, can realize the re-improvement of enterprise value management in the process of future financial development of enterprises, to continue to adhere to the intelligent financial management system construction. At the same time, the process of intelligent financial management system construction should be constantly adjusted so that all components of the enterprise can be better coordinated development in order to better enhance the value of the enterprise.

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